

The Whole Theory of This Universe—A Step Forward to Einstein

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Abstract

Last sentence of Einstein was, “Let me complete the Circle” and first sentence of our article is, “We have completed the circle”. We believed that the universe inside an atom is just like a galaxy of particles inside it and its sub-atomic particles, even every photon possess a galaxy of sub-photons inside it. Energy is stored in the form of energy pool in the center of each atom and sub-atomic particle. From this energy pool, particles are generating *i.e.* energy is converting into particles. While in some sub-atomic galaxies, particles are trapped by the energy pool *i.e.* particles are converting into energy. The magnification process unfolded the mysteries of atoms and galaxies. From magnified images of atoms and subatomic particles, we concluded that atom and galaxies are wrapped in folds. Also concluded that two types of matter present in the universe, luminous (e.g. stars) and non-luminous (e.g. planets, moons) matter. The center of luminous matter (galaxies) is known as white hole while the center of non-luminous matter (galaxies) is known as black hole. White holes and black holes are actually the energy pools.

Keywords

Explored, Atom, Galaxy, Energy Pool, Black Hole, White Hole, Recycling

1. Introduction

Cosmologists have calculated that the universe evolved over the past 13.8 billion years using two concepts that describe how matter is clustered in galaxies and Einstein’s theory of gravity, or general relativity, and which scientists use to calculate the extent of the universe’s expansion at any time [1]. We have the potential to take the next step towards a new theory which will explain the current puzzles [2]. Current measurements of the cosmic microwave background (CMB)

indicate that the total energy density is within 10% of the unit. Additionally, the estimates of Ω_M of mass, light, X-ray emissions, numbers and movements of clusters of galaxies that converge around 0.2 to 0.3 indicate a significant contribution through an energy vacuum, sufficient to produce the accelerated universe [3]. The movement of the sun with the restoration of the spectrum to an extragalactic nebula has sought a correlation between clear radial velocities and distances, but so far the results have not been convincing [4]. We live in a world accelerated with either a positive constant cosmologie or some other dark energy with a strongly negative pressure [5]. Dark energy was argued by the acceleration of the expansion of the universe but not measured directly. When we verify the data, this interpretation is based on the difference between the magnitodi observation and the calculated size of a particular red shift. But there are a lot of uncertain relationships [6]. The unexpected fainting of the high redshift type Ia Supernova (SNe Ia), as measured by two teams, has been interpreted as evidence that the expansion of universe is accelerating [3]. We offer a new numerical method for building models of neutron black hole star binary [7].

The previous findings on atomic structure are that, “electrons revolve around the nucleus while protons and neutrons are present in the nucleus and more than 100 subatomic particles are present in an atom”. Previous findings do not give satisfactory explanation about the energy stored in an atom. This theory gives a clear picture of an atom, subatomic particles, energy stored in an atom and subatomic particles, conversion of subatomic particles into energy and energy into subatomic particles. This theory reveals that there is no hard mass in the center of an atom but energy in the form of dense energy pool (saturated with trapped particles) or less dense (not fully saturated with trapped particles) is present in the center of an atom and in the center of subatomic particles. Particles in the form of particle galaxies are revolving around the central energy pool. Moreover subatomic particles are produced from this central energy pool. Some subatomic particles are trapped by this central energy pool for recycling and hence, the cycle is completed. Atoms and subatomic particles are wrapped in folds *i.e.* an atom consists of subatomic particles galaxies with central energy pool and each subatomic particle consists of sub-sub atomic particles galaxies with central energy pool and so on. We believe that the model of galaxies is similar to that of an atom, *i.e.* a galaxy is also wrapped in folds just like an atom with central energy pool (previously known as black hole) and each galaxy consists of sub-galaxies with their central energy pools (small black holes). And these sub-galaxies are further wrapped into folds of mini-galaxies, minor galaxies, micro galaxies and solar systems etc. New galaxies, solar systems, stars, planets etc. are produced from central energy pools (black holes) and older ones are entrapped by the central energy pools (black holes) for recycling and hence, cycle is completed.

(Black hole models contradicted by hands-on tests

Small cracks in basic theories

Date: August 28, 2017

Source: DOE/Sandia National Laboratories

Summary: Models of black holes that rely upon an assumption made 20 years ago need revision, explain investigators.)

According to a study published in the journal nature, the center of the Milky Way holds 10,000 small black holes that have been previously undetected (**Figure 1**). Some of these smaller black holes interact with the supermassive black hole known as Sagittarius A* at the core of the galaxy. According to Einstein's equation $E = mc^2$, mass and energy are interconvertible. So, this work gives a real proof of the validity of Einstein's equation at atomic level as well as at the milk way and other galaxies level. It also reveals that photons are material sub-sub-subatomic (etc.) particles and they also contain galaxies of smaller particles and energy pool.

Forget black holes, WHITE HOLES are weirder and "SPEWING matter from another universe". WHILE scientists are still struggling to explain exactly what a black hole is, they are now examining the possibility of a counter to the mysterious entities—white holes (**Figure 2**).

By Sean Martin

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2. Magnification of Images of Major Galaxy with Central White Hole

Many times magnified images of galaxy as given below. **Figures 3-13** are self-explanatory.

3. Images of Galaxies with Central Black Hole

Magnified images of galaxy many times, few are given below. **Figures 14-25** are self-explanatory.

Figure 1. NASA's image of black hole published in the journal nature.

Figure 2. Image PUBLISHED: 09:38, Thu, Apr 20, 2017|UPDATED: 13:04, Thu, Apr 20, 2017).

Figure 3. Major galaxy.

Figure 4. Magnified.

Figure 5. Magnified.

Figure 6. Magnified.

Figure 7. Magnified.

Figure 8. Magnified.

Figure 9. Magnified.

Figure 10. Magnified.

Figure 11. Magnified.

Figure 12. like Mini galaxy.

Figure 13. Central energy pool.

Figure 14. Magnification of NASA's image of black hole.

Figure 15. Sub-galaxies emerging from black hole.

Figure 16. Magnified.

Figure 17. Magnified.

Figure 18. Central black hole.

Figure 19. Birth of Minor galaxies from black hole (energy pool).

Figure 20. Minor galaxy with central white hole.

Figure 21. May be some solar system.

Figure 22. Mini galaxy with central black hole (energy pool). Micro galaxies are emerging from Central black hole (energy pool).

Figure 23. Micro-galaxy with central black hole.

Figure 24. Birth of Non luminous matter from central pool. While luminous matter is entrapped by central pole.

Figure 25. Micro-galaxy with central white hole.

4. Images of Atom and Subatomic Particles

Magnified images of atom, subatomic particles, energy pools, few are given below. **Figures 26-36** are self-explanatory.

Figure 26. Molecule.

Figure 27. Atom.

Figure 28. Magnified Atom with central energy pool.

Figure 29. Sub-atomic particle galaxy.

Figure 30. Subatomic particle galaxy emerging from central energy pool.

Figure 31. Sub-atomic particle galaxy.

Figure 32. Magnified.

Figure 33. Luminous Sub-atomic particle galaxy With central white hole.

Figure 34. Energy from central energy pool is converting into particles.

Figure 35. Energy from central energy pool is converting into particles.

Figure 36. Sub-atomic particles galaxies are trapped by central energy pool *i.e.* particles are converting into energy.

5. Explanation in Comparison

Same principles are working from atoms to galaxies. An atom is a true picture of galaxies. Just like a galaxy, in the center of an atom, an energy pool exists, from which subatomic particles are produced *i.e.* energy is converted into subatomic particles and vice versa. Major galaxies like our Milky Way also possess central energy pool known as black hole from which sub-galaxies are produced. Each subatomic particle is a galaxy inside it. Each atomic particle possesses an energy pool in its center just like an atom. Each subatomic particle consists of a galaxy of sub-subatomic particles with energy pool in its center. This process continued

to hundreds of times. Even photons possess galaxies inside them. Photons are material particles. They also possess galaxies of sub-photon particles inside them. Each sub-galaxy contains numerous mini galaxies inside it with central energy pool. And each mini-galaxy contains numerous minor galaxies inside it along with central energy pool etc. At the end each galaxy contains numerous solar systems. These are all wrapped in folds. Diagrammatically, it can be explained as, **Figure 37**.

6. Conclusions

This universe is wrapped in multi folds, even each galaxy and atom consists of multiple galaxies and multiple subatomic particles respectively. We believed that the atomic models and the models of galaxies are similar. Black holes and white holes are actually the energy pools. Energy pools exist in the center of atoms, subatomic particles, major galaxies, minor galaxies, mini galaxies, sub galaxies etc. from which new particles, planets, stars etc. are produced and older ones are recycled. It seems that same rules and principles are working from atoms to galaxies.

The whole theory of this universe is that “This universe is made up of two types of minute particles—anitron (negative) and catitron (positive). These are the first two particles generated from the energy *i.e.* energy is converted into matter in the form of anitron and catitron. When anitrons and catitrons combine in equal numbers, neutral particles generate like neutrons, photons etc. While when anitrons and catitrons combine in unequal numbers, either negatively charged particle (like electron) or positively charged particles (like protons, positrons) are produced depending on whether anitron or catitron is present in greater number. Electrostatic force of attraction is the only force and it is present between anitron and catitron. At the level of macro bodies like solar

Figure 37. Similarities between atom and galaxy. Atoms and Galaxies all are wrapped in folds.

Figure 38. Conversion of energy into matter.

Figure 39. conversion of matter into energy.

system and galaxies it is named as gravitational force. Gravitational force is actually the electrostatic force originated from the micro galaxies of atomic and subatomic particles which shows the collective response at solar system and galaxies levels. Same principles are working from atom to solar system and galaxies. Just like an atom, there is energy pool in the center of each galaxy from which new smaller galaxies, solar systems, planets or stars are produced. And the older ones fall in the energy pool or are entrapped by the energy pool (black hole) for recycling and hence, the cycle is completed.” (Figure 38 & Figure 39) Future work, unification force theory, how all the forces merge into a single electrostatic force? Further investigations can be made in this regard. Structures of compounds can be explained by using magnification process.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- [1] Cho, A. (2017) Is Dark Energy an Illusion? *Science*.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal0994>

- <http://www.sciencemag.org/news/2017/04/dark-energy-illusion>
- [2] Perlmutter, S. (2003) Supernovae, Dark Energy, and the Acceleration Universe. *Physics Today*, **56**, 53-60. <http://www-supernova.lbl.gov/PhysicsTodayArticle.pdf>
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1580050>
- [3] Riess, A.G. (2000) The Case for an Accelerating Universe from Supernovae. *PASP*, 1-33. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/astro-ph/0005229.pdf>
- [4] Hubble, E. (1929) A Relation between Distance and Radial Velocity among Extra-Galactic Nebulae. *The Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, **15**, 168-173. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.15.3.168>
https://apod.nasa.gov/diamond_jubilee/d_1996/hub_1929.html
- [5] Perlmutter, S. (1999) Supernovae, Dark Energy, and the Accelerating Universe: The Status of the Cosmological Parameters. *Lepton and Photon Interactions at High Energies*, 733-757.
<http://www.slac.stanford.edu/econf/C990809/docs/perlmutter.pdf>
- [6] Serret, O. (2018) Gravity vs. Dark Energy, about the Expansion of the Universe. *Journal of Modern Physics*, **9**, 84-97.
<https://www.scirp.org/journal/PaperInformation.aspx?PaperID=81830>
- [7] Baumgarte, T.W., Skoge, M.L. and Shopiro, S.L. (2004) Black Hole-Neutron Star Binaries in General Relativity: Quasiequilibrium Formulation. *Physical Review D*, **70**, Article ID: 064040. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.70.064040>